

Ligational Behaviour of a New Pyrazole-derived Tridentate : Mixed Ligand Complexes of Cobalt(II) with 1-Nitroguanyl- 5-Methyl Pyrazole-3-Carboxylic Acid and Heterocyclic Amines

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New mixed ligand complexes of cobalt(II) with 1-nitroguanyl-5-methyl pyrazole-3-carboxylic acid as the primary ligand and heterocyclic amines (as the co-ligand) have been prepared and characterised. The magnetic and electronic spectral features of metallic complexes are consistent with an average octahedral environment of the ligands around the central cobalt(II) ion and the ligand field parameters tacitly support such proposition. The i.r. spectra of the metal complexes indicate that the primary ligand is coordinated through the pyrazolyl nitrogen, the carboxylic oxygen and the nitrogen of the nitroguanyl group, thus showing tridentate (ONN) behaviour. The derivatographic studies have been useful in having an idea regarding the thermal stability and the mode of cleavage of the complex species.

PYRAZOLE-derivatives have long been acclaimed for their medicinal values and recently certain pyrazolo-pyrimidines are being studied in the fight against cancer¹. The coordination chemistry of pyrazole-derived ligands has received much attention² in current years, primarily because of the biological importance of these heterocyclic bases which contain potential donor sites. However, most of the studies including recent work from our laboratory^{3,4} have centred around synthesis and structural studies on the metal complexes of pyrazole containing bidentates. Till date, the only report of a pyrazole-derived tridentate, to our knowledge, is 1-(8-hydroxy 2-quinolyl)-3,5-dimethyl pyrazole⁵ which has been proposed for the determination of cadmium by measuring the luminescence of the metal chelate. As a part of our programme devoted to a systematic study of the chelating tendencies of new pyrazole-based tridentates, we wish to report here the synthesis and structural characterisation (from magnetic, spectral and derivatographic studies) of cobalt(II) complexes with 1-nitroguanyl-5-methyl pyrazole-3-carboxylic acid (henceforth abbreviated as NMPCH₂), a potential tridentate, synthesised for the first time in our laboratory.

Experimental

All reagents used were of A.R. grade and the solvents were purified before use.

Preparation of the ligand (NMPCH₂):

1-Nitroguanyl-5-methyl pyrazole-3-carboxylic acid was prepared by the condensation of sodium

salt of ethyl acetopyruvate with nitro-aminoguanidine⁶ following a method very similar to that adopted by Knorr and Macdonald⁷ for the synthesis of 5(3)-methyl pyrazole-3(5)-carboxylic acid. The product on recrystallisation from hot ethanol produced a white crystalline compound, m.p. 189°. (Found : C, 33.80 ; H, 3.28 ; N, 32.86 ; C₆H₇N₅O₄ requires C, 33.70 ; H, 3.24 ; N, 32.82%).

Preparation of the mixed ligand complexes :

(a) Co(NMPC).3H₂O

Ethanollic solutions of hydrated cobalt(II) chloride (0.005 mole) and the ligand (0.005 mole) were mixed together. The resulting solution was adjusted to have pH ≈ 5-6 by dilute ammonia solution ; the pink microcrystalline compound separated out within few minutes, this was filtered off, washed with water and alcohol and then dried over fused calcium chloride.

(b) Co(NMPC).B.2H₂O (B = py, β-pico and γ-pico)

A solution of hydrated Co(II) chloride (0.005 mole) in ethanol was mixed with a solution of the ligand (0.005 mole) in the same solvent followed by the addition of the respective base to have pH of the reaction mixture around 5-6. The resultant compounds were collected as above.

(c) Co(NMPC).α-pico

The same preparative method outlined as in (b) was followed except that the reaction mixture was

refluxed to isolate the compound as shining deep pink crystals.

(d) $\text{Co}(\text{NMPC}) \cdot \text{B} \cdot n\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (B=bipy, *o*-phen, $n=2,3$)

The resulting solution obtained by mixing ethanolic solutions of hydrated cobalt(II) chloride (0.005 mole) and the ligand (0.005 mole) was treated with ethanolic solution of the respective base (0.005 mole). To this was added dilute ammonia solution to have $\text{pH} \approx 5-6$ and then left at room temperature ($\sim 25^\circ$) for about an hour. The microcrystalline compound separated, in each case, was collected as before.

Physical measurements and analyses :

The physico-chemical measurements like diffuse reflectance spectra, infrared spectra and magnetic susceptibilities in the solid state were carried out as described earlier⁹. The electronic solution spectra were taken on a Hilger-Watts UVISPEK spectrophotometer using DMF as solvent in a cell of 1 cm light path. Derivatographic analyses were done with the help of a Hungarian derivatograph [DERIVATOGRAPH ; System : Paulik, F., Paulik, J. and Erdey, L., MOM (Budapest)]. The cobalt content in the complexes was determined gravimetrically as CoSO_4 . C, H and N analyses were performed micro-analytically.

Results and Discussion

The condensation product of ethylacetylpyruvate and nitroaminoguanidine is characterised as 1-nitroguanyl-5-methyl pyrazole-3-carboxylic acid(I) from elemental analyses and from a knowledge of the mode of formation of pyrazole derivatives⁸.

The acid dissociation constants of the ligand, NMPCH_2 , determined potentiometrically by Bjerrum method give values of $\text{pk}_2^* = 3.92$ and $\text{pk}_1^* = 8.96$ which correspond to the deprotonation from the carboxylic group and the nitroguanyl group respectively; this fact indicates that the ligand has the potentiality of showing a diprotic (tridentate) function in forming metallic complexes at controlled pH values.

Magnetic and electronic spectral features :

Analytical data (Table 1) show the present mixed ligand complexes to conform to the general composition $\text{Co}(\text{NMPC}) \cdot \text{B} \cdot n\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (B= H_2O or

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND MAGNETIC DATA FOR THE COMPLEXES

Complex	Colour	Found(%)		Calc.(%)		μ_{eff} at 304°K
		N	Metal	N	Metal	
$\text{Co}(\text{NMPC}) \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$	pink	21.60	18.16	21.61	18.22	4.50
$\text{Co}(\text{NMPC}) \cdot \text{py} \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	deep pink	21.93	15.33	21.32	15.32	4.52
$\text{Co}(\text{NMPC}) \cdot \alpha\text{-pico}$	deep pink	23.08	16.12	23.14	16.26	4.76
$\text{Co}(\text{NMPC}) \cdot \beta\text{-pico} \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	dirty pink	20.99	14.72	21.05	14.80	5.52
$\text{Co}(\text{NMPC}) \cdot \gamma\text{-pico} \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	dirty pink	21.15	14.54	21.05	14.80	4.84
$\text{Co}(\text{NMPC}) \cdot \text{bipy} \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$	pink	20.26	12.37	20.40	12.29	5.14
$\text{Co}(\text{NMPC}) \cdot \text{o-phen} \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	pink	20.27	12.16	20.08	12.09	4.85

N-heterocyclic base). The complexes are insoluble in water and in all the innocent organic solvents, but except the α -picoline adduct, they are fairly soluble in coordinating solvents like DMF, DMSO, etc.

The room temperature magnetic moments for the present cobalt(II) complexes lying between 4.50-5.14 B.M. are in some cases lower than those usually expected for high-spin octahedral cobalt(II) complexes. This lowering in magnetic moment values could be due to an orbital singlet ground state with a distorted octahedral stereochemistry of the complexes as is also supported by the electronic spectral data¹⁰. A small but perceptible increase in the moment values of the complexes $\text{Co}(\text{NMPC}) \cdot \text{B} \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in the order of the coligated base (B) $\text{py} \leq \beta\text{-pico} < \alpha\text{-pico} < \gamma\text{-pico}$ may be reconciled in terms of increasing basicity as well as increasing donor properties of these co-ligands in the same order¹¹.

In the reflectance spectra of the complexes, two principal bands located around 8500-10000 and 19000-21000 cm^{-1} may be assigned as a first approximation to the spin-allowed transitions ${}^4\text{T}_{1g}(\text{F}) \rightarrow {}^4\text{T}_{2g}(\text{F})(\nu_1)$ and ${}^4\text{T}_{1g}(\text{F}) \rightarrow {}^4\text{T}_{1g}(\text{P})(\nu_8)$ respectively in an average field of octahedral (O_h) symmetry¹². The split components of ν_8 (appearing as shoulders or very weak bands) may be attributed to the presence of low symmetry (approximating to C_2) components in the ligand field¹³. Using Ballhausen relationships¹⁴ the ligand field parameters (Dq, B) have been calculated (Table 2). The B values (741-885 cm^{-1}) which are significantly less than the free ion (971 cm^{-1}) value, indicate considerable overlap and delocalisation of the d-orbitals of the metal. The calculated band positions for ν_2 , using $\nu_2 = \nu_1 + 10\text{Dq}$ lie in the region 18180-19930 cm^{-1} (Table 2) and thus, only in case of $\text{Co}(\text{NMPC}) \cdot \text{py} \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, the observed weak band near 18000 cm^{-1} may tentatively be attributed

TABLE 2—ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL BANDS AND LIGAND FIELD PARAMETERS OF THE COMPLEXES

Complex	Medium	Absorption maxima $\nu(\text{cm}^{-1})(\epsilon)$	ν_3	ν_2	Dq (cm^{-1})	B (cm^{-1})	β^*
			Calc.	obs.			
Co(NMPC).3H ₂ O	Reflectance	20400 ; 16400wsh ; 9300	19810	—	1050	819	0.84
	DMF	20000sh(30.3) ; 18180(26.6) ; 16670sh(15.0)					
Co(NMPC).py.2H ₂ O	Reflectance	21800sh ; 20600 ; 18000 ; 9500wsh	18180	18000	968	885	0.91
	DMF	18520(24.5)					
Co(NMPC). α -pico	Reflectance	20500sh ; 19000 ; 17400 ; 9000	—	—	1011	741	0.76
Co(NMPC). β -pico.2H ₂ O	Reflectance	20000 ; 15800sh ; 9200 ; 8700	19570	—	1037	798	0.82
	DMF	18690(25.5)					
Co(NMPC). γ -pico.2H ₂ O	Reflectance	20400 ; 9300	19810	—	1050	819	0.84
	DMF	18520(25.2)					
Co(NMPC).bipy.3H ₂ O	Reflectance	20000 ; 16400wsh ; 9300	19790	—	1048	790	0.81
	DMF	18180(27.0)					
Co(NMPC).o-phen.2H ₂ O	Reflectance	21400sh ; 20200 ; 1300sh ; 9400	19980	—	1058	799	0.82
	DMF	18520(26.2)					

$\beta^* = B/B_0 = B/970$ (B_0 = the Racah parameter value in the free ion state). C. K. Jorgensen, *Advan. Chem. Phys.*, 1963, **5**, 33.

TABLE 3—SOME CHARACTERISTIC I.R. BANDS (4000-600 cm^{-1}) OF THE LIGAND (NMPCH₂) TOGETHER WITH THE COMPLEXES

Compound	N-H stretching mixed with O-H stretching	$\nu_{\text{asy}}(\text{OCO}^-)$	$\nu_{\text{sy}}(\text{OCO}^-)$	Coordinated water	Characteristic vibrations of secondary co-ligands
NMPCH ₂	3340s 3170s	1720vs	1450s	—	—
Co(NMPC).3H ₂ O	3280sb	1600ms	1460w	875mb	—
Co(NMPC).py.2H ₂ O	3330sb	1620vs	1450s	885sb	1570ms ; 1480br ; 1460s
Co(NMPC). α -pico	3300sb	1610vs	1465ms	—	1565ssh ; 1480ms ; 1460s
Co(NMPC). β -pico.2H ₂ O	3280sb	1590vs	1470s	990m	1560ms ; 1480ssh ; 1430ms
Co(NMPC). γ -pico.2H ₂ O	3330sb	1640sb	1460ms	880sb	1580ms ; 1490s ; 1460ssh
Co(NMPC).bipy.3H ₂ O	3280sb	1610sb	1460s	870s	1440vs ; 1070ms ; 760s ; 730vs
Co(NMPC).o-phen.2H ₂ O	3330sb	1640sb	1450ms	885m	1430vs ; 860sh ; 730mb

s=strong ; v=very ; m=medium ; b=broad ; sh=shoulder.

to the ν_3 transition (in O_h). Moreover, this calculation does suggest that the shoulders around 16000-17000 cm^{-1} are not due to ν_3 transition and are likely to be the spin-forbidden transition ${}^4T_{1g}(\text{F}) \rightarrow {}^2T_{2g}(\text{G})^{15}$. The DMF solution of the complexes exhibits a main band around 18000-19000 (ν_3) ($\epsilon < \sim 30 \text{ cm}^{-1} \text{ mole}^{-1}$) often accompanied with shoulders (Table 2) which might be taken as characteristic of distorted octahedral geometry. The shift of the absorption bands to lower frequency side as compared to the reflectance spectra suggest some sort of solvation.

I.R. Spectra :

The I.R. spectra (Table 3) in the present study proved to be of limited use in characterising the compounds due to the similarity of the ring systems, viz. the primary pyrazole ring and the secondary co-ligands py, pico, bipy, phen, etc. involved in complexation ; however definite information has been gathered regarding the participation of carboxyl and nitroguanyl ($-\text{C}=\text{NH}$) group of

NMPCH₂ in complex formation. All spectra (of the metal complexes show absorption characteristics

of the aromatic ligands and all show absorption characteristics of the asymmetric (at 1590-1640 cm^{-1} as compared to 1720 cm^{-1} in the free ligand) and symmetric (1450-1470 cm^{-1}) ν_{COO^-} for coordinated carboxylate group attached to the pyrazole ring. The IR spectrum of the primary ligand, NMPCH₂, shows two strong bands at 3340 and 3170 cm^{-1} which are assigned to $\nu_{\text{asy}}(\text{N-H})$ and $\nu_{\text{sy}}(\text{N-H})$ modes of vibration respectively¹⁶ of the nitroguanyl group ; these bands disappear and a strong broad band at ca. 3280-3330 cm^{-1} appears in the i.r. spectra of the metal complexes thereby suggesting deprotonation of one of the N-H groups in complexation forming nitrogen to metal bond¹⁷. However, the diffuse character and broadness of this band indicate inter or intramolecular hydrogen bonding between amide ($=\text{NH}$) group and H₂O molecules present in the complexes. The i.r. spectrum of Co(NMPC).3H₂O recorded down to 250 cm^{-1} shows one strong absorption in the region 310-320 cm^{-1} which is absent in the free ligand ; therefore it seems reasonable to assign this band to M-N (ring) stretching mode¹⁸ giving positive indication of the pyrazole nitrogen being bonded to the metal ion ; this conclusion is in agreement with X-ray crystallographic studies of several pyrazole-metal complexes^{19,20}. The characteristic vibration of the secondary co-ligands (py, pico, bipy, phen, etc.)

present (Table 3) in the metal complexes agree well with those reported earlier showing their coordinated nature in the corresponding adducts^{21,22}. Moreover, the hydrated complexes, $\text{Co}(\text{NMPC}) \cdot \text{B} \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ ($\text{B} = \text{H}_2\text{O}$, py , β or γ -picoline) show an additional band around $880\text{-}990\text{ cm}^{-1}$ characteristic of the rocking mode of coordinated water²³ while the absence of any such band in the spectra of bipyridyl and phenanthroline adducts indicates that water molecules are not coordinated in these species; the results of thermal analyses (see below) of the compounds also support this proposition.

Derivatographic studies :

The DTG and DTA peaks in the derivatograms of the primary ligand (NMPCH_2) and the complex species indicate in a stepwise manner the loss of water (both coordinated and lattice water molecules at different temperatures) and secondary base molecules followed by simultaneous decarboxylation and loss of the nitroguanyl group; however, except the anhydrous species none of the intermediates could be isolated. The final conversion of the complex species to cobalt oxide is complete around 450° .

Conclusion :

It appears, therefore, that the ligand 1-nitroguanyl-5-methyl pyrazole-3-carboxylic acid (NMPCH_2) functions as a diprotic (ONN) tridentate in forming the present $\text{Co}(\text{II})$ complexes coligated with either water molecule or heterocyclic amines; in general the seemingly pentacoordinate monomeric complex species (as evidenced from i.r. and thermal analysis) appear polymeric octahedral having approximating C_2 -symmetry (as evidenced from electronic spectra) where the polymerisation might be effective through additional bonding sites of either the nitroguanyl or the carboxyl group of the primary ligand molecule.

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